

Whole Blood Viscosity and Diabetic Microvascular Disease

*Robert M. Peters

Zucker School of Medicine, 500 Hofstra Blvd., Hempstead, New York, 11549 USA

*Corresponding author: [Robert M. Peters, MD, FACC \(Emeritus\), MBA](#)

Zucker School of Medicine, 500 Hofstra Blvd., Hempstead, New York, 11549 USA

Abstract

Whole blood viscosity (WBV) has been reported to be elevated in patients with diabetes [1]. This article presents studies showing that elevated WBV may play an important part in the development of diabetic microvascular disease (DMD). Although there are many biochemical and cellular elements involved in the pathogenesis of DMD, elevated WBV appears to play an important role in the diabetic microcirculation. This is due in part to the ability of increased WBV to adversely affect red blood cell (RBC) deformability, and to promote RBC aggregation leading to obstruction, slow flow, tissue hypoxia, and subsequent vascular and organ damage, including diabetic retinopathy, nephropathy, and neuropathy. Clinical trials should be undertaken to see if measurements of WBV could be useful to the clinician managing diabetic patients, including those with or at risk for DMD.

Keywords: Whole blood viscosity diabetic microvascular disease.

Introduction:

WBV is a measure of the thickness, or stickiness, of whole blood. It is determined by a simple blood test using a viscometer. The normal range is 1.5-3.0 centipoise. Symptoms rarely occur below a level of 4.0. These can include headache, fatigue, chest pain, visual changes, chest pain, paresthesias, and others. Conditions associated with elevated WBV include various hematological conditions (Waldenstrom's), certain malignancies, infections, hypertension, smoking, old age, hyperlipidemia, Type 1 and Type 2 diabetes, pre-diabetes, insulin resistance, metabolic syndrome, DMD, and diabetic retinopathy, nephropathy, and neuropathy (2).

Whole blood is a non-Newtonian fluid, which simply means that in areas of slow flow (low velocity, low shear rate), the WBV increases (3). This resulting stagnation enables RBCs to interact with various proteins, causing aggregation (rouleau formation) (4). Perhaps more important is that in this setting RBC deformability is decreased—membrane changes make the RBCs more rigid. Since the vessel size in the microcirculation is about 4-6 μm , and an RBC is about 8 μm , deformability is critical for RBCs to pass through. Rigidity leads to further stagnation, slower flow, obstruction, decreased oxygen delivery, tissue hypoxia, and vascular and tissue damage (5). Treatment usually involves treatment of the underlying disease, maintaining hydration, possible use of ASA, and other modalities. Some studies have found that in diabetics, reducing the glycohemoglobin level, reduced the WBV (6).

Methods:

A literature search was conducted.

Results:

DMD can have serious adverse effects not only on the retina, kidney, and nervous system, but also on the skin, heart, and skeletal muscle. Research appears to show that multiple cellular elements and biochemical pathways are involved (7). Hyperglycemia leads to cell signaling dysfunction, toxic metabolites (including activation of the diacylglycerol-protein kinase pathway, and the kallikrein-kinin system), with production of superoxide, inflammatory cytokines, and reactive oxygen species, leading to increased RBC oxidative stress (7). This causes impaired RBC deformability, increased RBC

aggregation, endothelial injury, increased WBV, obstruction and perfusion impairment, increased small vessel resistance, tissue hypoxia, and end-organ damage (8). Thus increased WBV is involved in the pathogenesis of DMD (9,10).

Discussion:

Given the above, it seems reasonable to begin clinical trials regarding WBV in diabetes with and without DMD). Such trials may answer such questions as:

1. What is the sensitivity, specificity, and predictive value of WBV in diabetes with and without DMD?
2. Does increased WBV depend on the age of the patient, or the type and duration of the diabetes?
3. Are patients with increased WBV but no sign of DMD at higher risk for development of DMD?
4. Should patients with normal WBV and no sign of DMD be screened periodically for an increased WBV?
5. Should any diabetic with or without DMD but having an elevated WBV have more intensive diabetic or specific treatment?
6. Can elevated WBV be lowered with better glucose control and possibly other treatments?

Answers to these types of questions may better help clinicians in using WBV to manage patients, and hopefully reduce the incidence, progression, and complications of DMD. Although the American Diabetic Association in its recent 2025 guidelines did not issue any specific recommendation regarding WBV (11), a recent 20 year bibliometric review lists several studies supporting the need for further clinical trials (12). All such trials should be done only using WBV (not plasma or serum viscosity), as only WBV detects resistance to flow (13).

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